

Analysis of the Translation Technique for "Easy" Song Lyrics from English to Indonesian in the Video Clip by Troye Sivan

Rahma Ayu Nadya Safira¹, Mochamad Nuruz Zaman²

¹ Universitas Terbuka. E-mail: ranssafira@gmail.com

² Politeknik Negeri Jakarta. E-mail: mzaman@bispro.pnj.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Adaptation, literal translation, translation techniques, transposition

How to cite:

Safira, R. A. N., & Zaman, M. N. (2023). Analysis of the Translation Technique for "Easy" Song Lyrics from English to Indonesian in the Video Clip by Troye Sivan. *English Education, Linguistics, and Literature Journal*, 2(2), 11-23.

ABSTRACT

The increasingly global use of digital music platforms is of course very helpful for artists to introduce their work to all fans from various walks of life and languages around the world. One of which was done by an artist named Troye Sivan, who included hard subtitles in the Indonesian language in the video clip for the song "Easy". This study aims to find out what techniques are used in the process of translating the lyrics of the song "Easy" by Troye Sivan. The research method used is descriptive qualitative and uses the translation theory of Molina and Albir. The results of this study are that there are 5 translation techniques used, namely: Literal Translation with 20 data, Adaptation with 7 data, Compensation with 1 data, Transposition with 2 data.

1. Introduction

The global music industry has experienced an unprecedented boom in recent years. The increasing availability of various digital platforms and streaming services has made music more accessible to anyone and anywhere. As a result, various music from various languages and cultures are heard by listeners all over the world. These artists are also competing to be able to connect with their fans in various parts of the world who speak different languages. One way that the artist can do is to make subtitles using another language. However, these differences have created new challenges for translators in translating song lyrics from one language to another. This is also very relevant to the existence of video clips with hard subtitle, subtitles that are already attached to videos or films and cannot be edited, where the translation of the song lyrics must be accompanied by visual symbols and other audio-visual elements that can convey message from the artist effectively.

Translation is a process of reproducing source language as natural and as close as possible into an equivalent target language, including in meaning and style of language.

(Nida & Taber 1982: 12). Meanwhile, in Hikmasari (2020: 12-13), Catford (1965: 20) argues that translation is a process of transferring equivalent text material from one language to another. Translation of song lyrics is a complex job and requires a parallel understanding between source language and target language. The main purpose of translation is to transfer the meaning of source language text into target language or another language (Budiman et al., 2023). For this reason, the translator must find the most effective way to capture the gist of the original lyrics while also ensuring that the original version of the song lyrics. Catford (1965) himself said that the main problem in translation is finding the right equivalent in target language, where the conditions and characteristics must be explained by a theory. The translator must be able to understand the material to be translated with the aim of being able to analyze and convey the meaning of the material, which means the translator must understand the meaning of the lyrics of the song to be translated.

Troye Sivan is a singer and actor from Australia who started his career in 2006 by starring in a musical called *Seven Perth Telethon*. In his musical career, he started his musical career by releasing the mini album *Dare to Dream* in June 2007. Troye Sivan gave birth to various songs that were booming among young people entitled "Angel Baby", "I'm So Tired", and "Strawberry and Cigarettes". He has also won several international awards and also collaborated with several Hollywood singers.

The song "Easy", which was released on July 15, 2020, is included in his album entitled *In a Dream*. This song was written by Oscar Michael Gorres, Troye Sivan, Kacey Musgraves. Quoted from LirikTerjemahan.id and OldTimeMusic.com, Easy tells of a love relationship that starts to break down because one of their partners makes a mistake. Then the two couples started to mend their relationship again. Uniquely, in the video clip for the song Easy, Troye Sivan inserts a hard subtitle of the lyrics of the song in Indonesian, which later becomes a source of research in this scientific work.

The problem formulation raised in this scientific work is how to analyze the translation technique for "Easy" song lyrics from English to Indonesian in the video clip by Troye Sivan. With this scientific work, the author aims to find out what techniques are used in the process of translating the song lyrics. The research source for this scientific work, namely the song "Easy" by Troye Sivan, was taken in the video clip for the song through its official YouTube channel, Troye Sivan.

2. Research Methodology

The methodology used in this scientific work is qualitative descriptive. Qualitative descriptive method is a comprehensive approach used to explore and explain a phenomenon or social event in depth. The qualitative methodology itself is a research based on the philosophy of positivism, which is used as a tool for natural research, not in an experimental state (Sugiyono, 2019). Meanwhile, according to Walidin and Tabrani (2015: 77), qualitative research is a research process that aims to understand social or human phenomena by creating a comprehensive and complex picture by presenting data in the form of words, reports of detailed views from informant sources, and in a natural situation (not in the setting). This methodology focuses on the complexity of understanding a specific research topic by collecting detailed data through various qualitative techniques, such as the ability of analysis, synthesis, description, and

evaluation of the researcher. This methodology seeks to provide a comprehensive and holistic explanation of the subject under investigation, capturing its context, meaning and interpretation.

The type of data used in this study is a qualitative data. Qualitative data is the result of data collection that takes pictures, words or interviews rather than numbers (Emzir, 2011). It is in the form of the official video clip for the song "Easy" from the official YouTube channel Troye Sivan, which includes hard subtitles in the video. Qualitative data according to Emzir (2011: 3) is a collection of data that is taken in the form of pictures or sentences rather than data in the form of numbers.

The data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive and qualitative analysis. Data analysis is a process of organizing and searching field notes, interviews, and other materials collected by researchers in a systematic way. It is intended that researchers are able to understand the material well and make it easier for researchers to present their research results to the wider community. Descriptive analysis technique is a research method in which the data is actually collected, then the data is compiled, processed and analyzed so that an overview of the existing problems can be presented. Meanwhile, qualitative analysis according to Moleong (2007) is a research procedure that will produce descriptive data, such as written or spoken words from the behavior of the people being observed.

3. Findings and Discussion

In translation itself, there are several techniques that translators can use to translate one language into another. According to Vinay and Darbelnet (1985) in Molina and Albir (2002), there are seven translation procedures, namely borrowing, transposition, modulation, equivalence, calque, literal translation, and adaptation, which are then classified into two, namely direct or literal. (direct translation), where the techniques included are borrowing, calque, and literal translation, as well as oblique (oblique translation) which includes transposition, modulation, equivalence, and adaptation. Direct translation is carried out when there are exact structural, lexical, and also morphological similarities between the two languages, and can only be carried out when the two languages have similarities. Apart from these seven translation procedures, there are also complementary translation techniques, namely compensation, concentration, dissolution, amplification, economy, reinforcement, condensation, explicitation, implicitation, generalization, particularization, and also inversion.

However, Molina and Albir have formulated their own techniques by taking into account matters such as separating the concepts of translation techniques such as strategy, method, and also error; translation characteristics and language comparisons; translation function; terminology or retain common terms; and also techniques whose mechanisms have not been described previously. The techniques formulated by Molina and Albir (2002:509) are as follows:

1. Adaptation, which is a technique for explaining or expressing something using different situations by shifting or adapting to culture by using one of the elements from the target culture.

2. Amplification, is a technique that is used when TL uses more linguistic elements to cover syntactic or lexical gaps. This amplification technique is carried out by providing a more detailed or detailed explanation of a phrase or term.
3. Borrowing, is a technique that is carried out by taking expressions or words directly from another language. So, a word is taken directly or borrowed from a language to be a translation of that word into another language.
4. Calque, where this technique is carried out by inserting or translating a foreign word or phrase into another language with the actual meaning, which can be lexical or structural.
5. Compensation, which is a technique for conveying information elements elsewhere in a phrase or sentence because the stylistic effect of SL cannot be applied in the same place as TL.
6. Description, is a technique for replacing expressions or terms with descriptions of their functions and forms.
7. Discursive creation, is a technique for determining a temporary equivalent of an expression that is out of context and completely unpredictable.
8. Established equivalent, which is a translation technique using terms and expressions commonly used in TL to serve as equivalents.
9. Generalization is a technique for translating using more general terms. This technique is used to describe a context or situation in general (generalization).
10. Linguistic amplification is a translation technique to add some linguistic elements. Usually this technique is used in dubbing and interpreting.
11. Linguistic compression is a technique for synthesizing or combining linguistic elements in ST, which is usually used in simultaneous interpretation and subtitling.
12. Literal Translation, where this technique is carried out by translating foreign language phrases with their true meaning or translated literally into other languages from word to word.
13. Modulation, is a technique that is carried out by changing the point of view, focus, or shifting the cognitive category of a phrase.
14. Particularization is a translation technique using more precise terms.
15. Reduction, is a technique for suppressing information items from a sentence of the original language into an expression or term.
16. Substitution, is a translation technique that is used to change linguistic elements into paralinguistic elements such as gestures and intonation or vice versa. This technique is used in interpretation.
17. Transposition, where this technique is carried out by shifting word classes, where verbs are changed to nouns, nouns are changed to prepositions.

18. Variation, which is a translation technique used to change linguistic or paralinguistic elements such as gestures and intonation which affect aspects of linguistic variation, such as changing and adjusting speech tones.

In this discussion section, the writer uses several samples in the lyrics of the song "Easy". After being analyzed, the writer found several techniques used in translating the lyrics of the song.

Table 1. Song Lyrics Sample

No.	Song Lyrics	Translation Result	Analysis of Techniques
1	You ran away to find something to say	<i>Kamu lari untuk mencari kata-kata</i>	Literal Translation
2	I went astray to make it okay	<i>Aku tersesat memastikan kamu tak apa-apa</i>	Literal Translation, Adaptation, Compensation
3	And he made it easy, darlin'	<i>Dia membuatnya mudah, sayang</i>	Literal Translation
4	I'm still in love and I say that because	<i>Aku masih sayang dan aku bilang karna</i>	Literal Translation
5	I know how it seems between you and me	<i>Aku tahu bagaimana rasanya kita</i>	Literal Translation, and Adaptation
6	It hasn't been easy darlin'	<i>Ini tidak mudah sayang</i>	Literal Translation
7	I can't even look at you	<i>Aku tak bisa menatapmu</i>	Literal Translation
8	Would you look at the space just next to your feet?	<i>Maukah kamu melihat ke tempat lain</i>	Literal Translation and Adaptation
9	The wood is warping, the lines distorting	<i>Kayu yang melengkung, garis yang berkelok</i>	Literal Translation
10	This house is on fire, woo!	<i>Rasa ini seperti api, wow!</i>	Adaptation
11	Burning the tears right off my face	<i>Melelehkan air mata yang terus menetes</i>	Transposition
12	What the hell did we do?	<i>Apa yang baru kita lakukan</i>	Adaptation
13	Tell me we'll make it through	<i>Katakan padaku kita akan baik-baik saja</i>	Literal Translation and Adaptation
14	'Cause he made it easy, easy	<i>Karna ia membuatnya mudah, mudah</i>	Literal Translation
15	Please don't leave me, leave me	<i>Kumohon jangan pergi, pergi</i>	Literal Translation
16	What's left of the dance?	<i>Apa yang tersisa dari dansa itu?</i>	Literal Translation
17	That's all on my hands	<i>Aroma di tanganku</i>	Transposition
18	The rock in my throat	<i>Batu di tenggorokanku</i>	Literal Translation
19	A hair on my coat	<i>Rambut di jaketku</i>	Literal Translation
20	The stranger at home, my darlin'	<i>Orang asing di rumahku sayangku</i>	Literal Translation

21	(Like some kind of freak, my darlin')	(Seperti orang aneh, sayangku)	Literal Translation
22	Now I'm vulnerable, so sad and alone	Sekarang aku galau, sedih dan sendiri	Adaptation and Literal Translation
23	But don't cry for me, 'cause everyone knows	Jangan kau menangis untukku, karna semua tahu	Literal Translation
24	You reap what you sow, my darlin'	Kamu menuai yang kamu tabur sayangku	Literal Translation

The results of the analysis of translation techniques on hard subtitles for the song lyrics of "Easy" by Troye Sivan, have found several techniques used by translators with the following discussion:

Data 1

ST: You ran away to find something to say

TT: *Kamu lari untuk mencari kata-kata*

On Data 1, pronoun "You" is translated literally as "*Kamu*," that which is identified in the Literal Translation technique and has the appropriate equivalent in Indonesian. The phrase "ran away" is translated as "*lari*," which "*lari*" has equivalent as "run" in English. Then in the phrase "to find something to say" translates to "*untuk mencari kata-kata*," which expresses the meaning of a search for words or something to say.

Data 2

ST: I went astray to make it okay

TT: *Aku tersesat memastikan kamu tak apa-apa*

The pronoun "I" is translated to "*Aku*" and the verb phrase "went astray" is translated to "*tersesat*," this translation shows that the technique used is Literal Translation. However, the Adaptation technique is also found in the results of this translation, "to make it okay" becomes "*memastikan kamu tak apa-apa*," where the phrase shows a different expression of meaning in the target language. In addition, there is also a Compensation technique as evidenced by the word "*memastikan*" which is used to compensate for the word "make" which is missing and not translated in this context. It can be concluded that in this verse there are Literal Translation, Adaptation, Compensation translation techniques.

Data 3

ST: And he made it easy, darlin'

TT: *Dia membuatnya mudah, sayang*

The phrase "And he made it easy, darlin'" is translated as "*Dia membuatnya mudah, sayang*" contains the Literal Translation technique. The pronoun "he" translates to "*dia*," which has a literal equivalent to the target language. The verb phrase "made it easy" is

translated as "*membuatnya mudah*". Meanwhile, the term "darlin" is translated as "sayang" in Indonesian.

Data 4

ST: I'm still in love and I say that because

TT: *Aku masih sayang dan aku bilang karna*

The result of the translation technique analysis used is the literal translation technique. In the phrase "I'm still in love" which is translated into "*Aku masih sayang*," then in the phrase "and I say that because" it becomes "*dan aku bilang karna*," where the phrase is translated without changing the structure and meaning of the word.

Data 5

ST: I know how it seems between you and me

TT: *Aku tahu bagaimana rasanya kita*

In this translation, it is analyzed that there are two techniques used, namely Literal Translation and Adaptation. There has been a change in the syntactic structure of the sentence in the translation results. The original sentence has the structure "how it seems between you and me", where the verb "seems" is followed by the prepositional phrase "between you and me". In the target language, the verb "seems" is replaced with the noun "*rasanya*" (feels/sensations) and is placed at the end of the sentence. The prepositional phrase "between you and me" is changed to "*kita*" (us) and is placed after "*rasanya*".

Data 6

TS: It hasn't been easy darlin'

TT: *Ini tidak mudah sayang*

Translation "It hasn't been easy, darlin'" to "*Ini tidak mudah, sayang*" involves the Literal Translation technique, where "*Ini*" refers to "It", "*tidak*" refer to "hasn't", and "*mudah*" refers to "been easy".

Data 7

TS: I can't even look at you

TT: *Aku tak bisa menatapmu*

The pronoun "I" translates to "*Aku*", which is the direct equivalent in the target language. The expression "can't even" translates as "*tak bisa*", maintains negation and conveys the inability to take action. The verb "look at" is translated as "*menatap*," which captures the meaning of directing one's gaze towards someone. The pronoun "you" is translated as "*mu*", which represents the object of the sentence. It can be concluded that the verses of this song contain Literal Translation techniques.

Data 8

TS: Would you look at the space just next to your feet?

TT: *Maukah kamu melihat ke tempat lain?*

Translation of "Would you look at the space just next to your feet?" to "*Maukah kamu melihat ke tempat lain?*" involves a combination of literal translation and adaptation techniques. "Would you look" is translated as "*Maukah kamu melihat,*" retaining the same meaning and structure. In the second part of the sentence, a slight adaptation is made to convey the same meaning in the target language. "at the space just next to your feet" is adapted to "*ke tempat lain*" which means "to another place". This adaptation technique allows the translator to choose a more idiomatic expression in the target language while maintaining the overall meaning and intent of the original sentence.

Data 9

TS: The wood is warping, the lines distorting

TT: *Kayu yang melengkung, garis yang berkelok*

The two part of lyrics of this song involve the Literal Translation technique, in which the original words and sentence structure are not changed and adapted to the original sentence. The noun phrase "The wood is warping" is translated as "*Kayu yang melengkung,*" where "*kayu*" means "wood", and "*melengkung*" means "warping" or "bending". Similarly, the noun phrase "the lines distorting" is translated as "*Garis yang berkelok,*" where "*garis*" means "lines", and "*berkelok*" means "distorting" or "curving".

Data 10

TS: This house is on fire, woo!

TT: *Rasa ini seperti api, wow!*

The translation of the verses of this song involves a translation technique known as Adaptation. In this translation there is an adaptation of the phrase "This house is on fire" which translates to "*Rasa ini seperti api,*" where "*rasa ini*" refers to a feeling or sensation and "*seperti api*" means "like fire." This Adaptation technique conveys the same idea of a house engulfed in flames but uses different words in the target language to evoke the intended emotion or perception. In addition, exclamations of "woo!" translates as "wow!" to convey surprise or joy.

Data 11

TS: Burning the tears right off my face

TT: *Melelehkan air mata yang terus menetes*

The verses of this song involve the Transposition technique, in this translation there is a change in the syntactic structure of the sentence. The original sentence has the structure "Burning the tears right off my face", where the verb "burning" is followed by the noun phrase "the tears" and the prepositional phrase "right off my face". In the target language, the verb "burning" is changed to "*melelehkan*" (melting) and is placed at the beginning of the sentence. The noun phrase "the tears" is changed to "*air mata*" and is placed after the verb. The prepositional phrase "right off my face" is changed to "*yang*

terus menetes" (that continuously trickles) and is placed after "*air mata*". This transposition technique rearranges the elements of the sentence to suit the linguistic conventions and wording of the target language.

Data 12

TS: What the hell did we do?

TT: *Apa yang baru kita lakukan*

The Adaptation translation technique is indicated in the translation results in the phrase "What the hell did we do?" which is translated as "*Apa yang baru kita lakukan*," where "what the hell" is interpreted as "*apa yang baru*", not "*Apa-apaan yang telah kita lakukan*," because the phrase "what the hell" expresses disbelief, surprise, and unsuspecting expression. Then "did we do." translates to "*kita lakukan*". This lyrics conveys the same sense of surprise or frustration that the original phrase conveys using different words in the target language. The use of the phrase "*apa yang baru*" captures the intended tone and emphasizes the appeal, whereas "*kita lakukan*" directly corresponds to the question of what is being done. Through this Adaptation technique, the translator ensures that the essential meaning and emotional impact of the original sentence is conveyed effectively in the target language.

Data 13

TS: Tell me we'll make it through

TT: *Katakan padaku kita akan baik-baik saja*

In the verses of this song, there is an indication of the Literal Translation technique, by translating the phrase "Tell me" to "*Katakan padaku*". Then the phrase "we'll make it through" is translated into "*kita akan baik-baik saja*," (in the literal sense "*kita akan melewatinya*") uses the Adaptation technique which conveys the meaning that the couple assures that they will make it through a difficult relationship situation. This technique allows the translator to choose phrases that can convey the same sense of certainty and resilience in the target language so that the overall meaning and tone the emotional content of the original sentence is conveyed effectively in the target language.

Data 14

TS: 'Cause he made it easy, easy

TT: *Karna ia membuatnya mudah, mudah*

Literal Translation techniques are used in this translation, as evidenced by the word "Cause" (from the word because) translated as "*Karena*", "he made it easy" to "*ia membuatnya mudah*," and "easy" translated to "*mudah*".

Data 15

TS: Please don't leave me, leave me

TT: *Kumohon jangan pergi, pergi*

The result of the technical analysis of the results of this translation is the Literal Translation technique. This can be seen from the word "Please" which is equated with

"Kumohon," then "don't leave me, leave me" is translated into "*jangan pergi, pergi*", where there is no change in the words or structure of the original sentence.

Data 16

TS: What's left of the dance?

TT: *Apa yang tersisa dari dansa itu?*

In this translation, the original words and sentence structures are retained in the target language, which indicates the Literal Translation technique. The question "*Apa yang tersisa*" is translated as "What's left", where "*what*" means "*apa*" and "*tersisa*" means "left" or "remaining". The prepositional phrase "of the dance" is translated as "*dari dansa itu*," which means "*dari tarian*". The essential meaning of the original sentence is conveyed effectively in the target language, raising questions about what remains or remains of the dance.

Data 17

TS: That's all on my hands

TT: *Aroma di tanganku*

The results of the translation of the lyrics use the Transposition technique. Instead of directly translating "That's all on my hands," which would be "*Itu semua di tangan saya*" the translator chose to use the metaphorical expression "*Aroma di tanganku*" (meaning scent in my hands) to convey the meaning that the all that remains of the dance they perform is the scent of the couple left in the songwriter's hand. This Transposition technique allows the translator to retain the metaphorical meaning of the original sentence while adapting it to the target language in a more idiomatic and evocative way.

Data 18

TS: The rock in my throat

TT: *Batu di tenggorokanku*

The translation results show the Literal Translation technique, where the resulting sentence does not change its meaning and the sentence structure becomes "*Batu di tenggorokanku*".

Data 19

TS: A hair on my coat

TT: *Rambut di jaketku*

The Literal Translation technique is indicated in the translation of this sentence, because it does not change the meaning and structure of the sentence in the translation, namely "Hair on my jacket."

Data 20

TS: The stranger at home, my darlin'

TT: *Orang asing di rumahku sayangku*

In the first part of the sentence, the translation technique Literal Translation is used, in which the words and the original sentence structure are retained in the target language. "The stranger at home" is translated as "*Orang asing di rumahku*", retaining the same meaning and structure. Then "my darlin'" is translated as "*sayangku*".

Data 21

TS: (Like some kind of freak, my darlin')

TT: (*Seperti orang aneh, sayangku*)

The results of this translation involve literal translation techniques. In the first part of the sentence, where "(Like some kind of freak)" is translated as "*(Seperti orang aneh)*," and "My darlin'" is translated as "*sayangku*", which retains the same meaning and structure.

Data 22

TS: Now I'm vulnerable, so sad and alone

TT: *Sekarang aku galau, sedih dan sendiri*

This sentence involves the Adaptation and Literal Translation techniques. In the first part of the sentence using the Adaptation translation technique, "Now I'm vulnerable" is translated as "*Sekarang aku galau*," where the word "vulnerable" means "*rentan*", which is then adapted in Indonesian to "*galau*". In the second part of the sentence, the Literal Translation technique is used. "so sad and alone" translates to "*sedih dan sendiri*", which conveys the same feeling of sadness and loneliness.

Data 23

TS: But don't cry for me, 'cause everyone knows

TT: *Jangan kau menangis untukku, karna semua tahu*

The results of this translation indicate that there is a literal translation technique. "But don't cry for me" translates to "*Jangan kau menangis untukku*," with the same meaning and structure. Then the phrase "'cause everyone knows" becomes "*karna semua tahu*", which does not change the meaning and word structure of the original sentence.

Data 24

TS: You reap what you sow, my darlin'

TT: *Kamu menuai yang kamu tabur sayangku*

The translation of the verses of the song involves the Literal Translation technique, in which the original words and sentence structures are retained in the target language. "You reap what you sow" is translated as "*Kamu menuai yang kamu tabur*," retaining the same meaning and structure. Later on "my darlin'" was adapted as "*sayangku*", which conveys the same affection and affection.

4. Conclusion

From the results of the author's analysis, there are six translation techniques used in translating the lyrics of the song "Easy" by Troye Sivan with the following details: Literal Translation of 20 data, Adaptation of 7 data, Compensation of 1 data, Transposition of 2 data. The lyrics of the song are translated using different techniques in order that the

translation results are acceptable in the target language and have a meaning as natural as possible in the target language. Molina & Albir (2002) argues that Literal Translation is a translation technique by translating source language phrases using equivalent words or literal meanings from the target language without changing the sentence structure. This can be seen from the overall translation of the lyrics of the song "Easy" which does not change the sentence structure and maintains the meaning word for word of the song phrase.

References

- Budiman, A., Wulandari, Y., & Rosyidah, N. (2023). Revisiting Newmark's Theory of Translation: To What Extent Is It Appropriate?. *Educalitra: English Education, Linguistics, and Literature Journal*, 2(1), 37-49.
- Catford, J. (1965). *A Linguistic Theory of Translation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Catford, J.C. (1974). *A Linguistic Theory of Translation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Diana, R. Penggunaan Metode dan Teknik Penerjemahan Pada Lirik Lagu "Mungkin Nanti" Karya Ariel NOAH ke dalam Bahasa Jepang Oleh Hiroaki Kato. *KIRYOKU*, 6(2), 85-94.
- Emzir, M., & Pd, M. (2012). *Metodologi penelitian kualitatif analisis data*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo.
- Hikmasari, M., & Sahayu, W. (2019). Unsur Budaya Material dalam Novel 'Entrok' Karya Okky Madasari. *Atavisme*, 22(2), 200-216.
- Kardijan, D. (2019). Analisis Penerjemahan Lirik Lagu "It's My Life" Karya Bon Jovi Versi Tautan <http://gudang-terjemahan-lagu.blogspot.co.id>. *Jurnal Siliwangi: Seri Pendidikan* P-ISSN, 5(1), 2019.
- Moleong, L. J. (2007). Metode penelitian kualitatif.
- Molina, L. & Albir, A. (2002). Translation Techniques Revisited: A Dynamic and Functionalist Approach. *Meta: Journal des traducteurs*. 47. 498. 10.7202/008033ar.
- Nida, E. A. & Taber. (1982). *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Leiden: E. J. Brill
- Sugiyono (2019). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung : Alfabet.
- Vinay, J. P., & Darbelnet, J. (1995). *Comparative stylistics of French and English: A methodology for translation* (Vol. 11). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Walidin, W., Saifullah, & Tabrani. (2015). *Metodologi penelitian kualitatif & grounded theory*. FTK Ar-Raniry Press.
- Wetzel, R. (2013). *The globalization of music in history* (Vol. 2). Routledge.
- Bicaramusik.id. (2020, 21 Juli). Troye Sivan Rilis "Easy" sebagai Nyanyian Patah Hati. Accessed on 27 May, 2023. <http://bicaramusik.id/berita/troye-sivan-easy/>
- Idntimes.com. (2022, 9 April) Biodata dan Profil Troye Sivan, Penyanyi Angel Baby Viral di TikTok. Accessed on 13 May, 2023. <https://www.idntimes.com/hype/entertainment/aulia-supintou-1/biodata-dan-profil-troye-sivan?page=all>
- Justrandomthings.com. (2020, 16 July). Troye Sivan – Easy | Lyrics Meaning & Song Review. Accessed on 16 May, 2023. <https://justrandomthings.com/2020/07/16/troye-sivan-easy-lyrics-meaning-song-review/>
- Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia Online. Accessed on 18 May, 2023. <https://kbbi.web.id/telop>
- Metodeku.com. (2020, 6 March). Perbedaan Hardsub Dan Softsub. Diakses pada 15 Mei 2023. <https://metodeku.com/perbedaan-hardsub-dan-softsub/>

- Oldtimemusic.com. (2023, 13 May). The Meaning Behind The Song: Easy by Troye Sivan. Accessed on 18 May, 2023. <https://oldtimemusic.com/the-meaning-behind-the-song-easy-by-troye-sivan/>
- Songmeaningsandfacts.com. (2020, 17 Juli) "Easy" by Troye Sivan. Accessed on 15 May, 2023. <https://www.songmeaningsandfacts.com/easy-by-troye-sivan/>
- Youtube.com. (2020, 14 Agustus). Troye Sivan-Easy (Indo Lyrics Video). Accessed on 10 May, 2023. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_JLa5vIrBew